

Isoquinoline Derivatives as Possible Amoebacides. Part III

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With regard to conjugation between the two aromatic rings in 1,1'-methylene-bis-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline, the effect of substitution at 3-position and of replacement of one of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group by an alkyl or aryl group have been studied.

In Part II¹ evidence, on the basis of ultraviolet absorption spectrum, has been adduced to show that 1,1'-methylene-bis-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline (II: $R_1=R_2=H$) exists in the form (III: $R_1=R_2=H$) with an exocyclic double bond. This base is characterised by a fine yellow colour and forms a monopicrate, whereas its dehydrogenated product, 1,1'-methylene-bis-isoquinoline, which exists in the normal endocyclic form (IV: $R_1=R_2=H$), forms a dipicrate. This characteristic of formation of mono- or dipicrate is now being found to be of general nature in compounds of this series and may be considered as a criterion to indicate the presence of an exocyclic double bond or the endocyclic form of the compound.

In course of extending the scope of the above observation, it is found that the presence of an alkyl group at 3-position does not affect the conjugation between the two aromatic rings. For example, malondi- α -methyl- β -phenethylamide (I: $R_1=H, R_2=Me$), when cyclised with phosphorus pentoxide, forms a yellow base, which, on the basis of ultraviolet spectrum (Table I), is considered to exist in the form (III: $R_1=H, R_2=Me$) and is characterised as monopicrate. Its dehydrogenated product (IV: $R_1=H, R_2=Me$) forms a dipicrate. It is of interest to note that the presence of an alkaryl group, such as benzyl, at the 3-position, however, shifts the equilibrium towards (II), as evidenced by the ultraviolet spectrum.

The study on the effect of replacement of one of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group in (II) by an alkyl or aryl group has also provided significant features. Methylmalondi- β -phenethylamide (I: $R_1=Me, R_2=H$) has, on cyclodehydration with phosphorus pentoxide, afforded a colorless base which forms a dipicrate. Ultraviolet absorption study of this compound in ethanolic solution shows that it exists in the normal endocyclic form (II: $R_1=Me, R_2=H$), whereas in ethanolic hydrogen chloride solution, in which it is found to develop a fine yellow colour, the ultraviolet spectrum indicates the presence of extended conjugation, showing that the compound under such condition exists as (III: $R_1=Me, R_2=H$). This appears to be a general phenomenon with the bases obtained from (I: $R_1=R_2=$ alkyl) by cyclodehydration. In ethanolic solution these are found to exist in the form (II), whereas in ethanolic hydrogen chloride solution they exist in the form (III). In order to study the effect of a similar replacement by phenyl, phenylmalondi- β -phenethylamide (I: $R_1=Ph, R_2=H$) has been cyclised in the usual manner with phosphorus pentoxide, when a yellow base has been obtained, which appears to be light-sensitive and quickly

1. This Journal, 1960, 37, 287.

turns pasty. As this base gives a picrate, agreeing on analysis with the monopicate of 1,1'-phenylmethylene-bis-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline, it may be rational to consider that it exists as (III: $R_1 = \text{Ph}$, $R_2 = \text{H}$) with an exocyclic double bond. As expected, its dehydrogenated product, 1,1'-phenylmethylene-bis-isoquinoline (IV: $R_1 = \text{Ph}$, $R_2 = \text{H}$) furnishes a dipicrate.

The ultraviolet absorption data for the above compounds are summarised in Table I and reveal the structural forms in which these are found to exist in ethanol or in ethanolic hydrogen chloride solution.

The triad system (II $\rightleftharpoons$ III) represents a case of imine-enamine tautomerism in 1,1'-methylene-bis-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline derivatives and the stability of (III) may be attributed to the possibility of proton bonding between the two nitrogen atoms² and to the cross conjugation of the enamine double bond with the extended conjugation of the aromatic nucleus.

The amoebicidal action of the compounds *in vitro* was studied by Dr. A. N. Bose and Shri S. Bose of this Institute either in Boeck and Drohbolz medium or in Pavlova medium. The *in vivo* activity was determined by noting the mean scores of young immature weanling rats (30-40 g.) inoculated intracoeccally with 100000-120000 highly motile amoebae (the strain *Entamoeba histolytica*, brand BIUS) contained in 0.3 ml of the medium. The drugs were fed daily for 5 days, starting from the next day of inoculation. The compound, 1,1'-methylene-bis-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline (II: $R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{Me}$), which, however, exists in the form (III: $R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{Me}$), is active at a dose range of 200 mg./kg./day. Other compounds have not shown so far any appreciable activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Phenyl-2-aminohexane.—The intermediate ketone (benzyl butyl ketone), required for the preparation of this amine, was obtained as follows: To sodium (20 g.), dissolved in ethanol (220 ml), benzyl cyanide (70 g.) and ethyl valerate² (125 g.) were added and

2. Noller *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **72**, 17; 1952, **74**, 3935.

the mixture was heated under reflux for 7 hours. The cyanoketone formed was extracted in the usual way and heated with a mixture of HCl (conc., 650 ml) and glacial acetic acid (570 ml) for 30 hours. Benzyl butyl ketone (70 g.) was extracted with ether and distilled at 130-31°/12 mm. This ketone (30 g.) was converted into 1-phenyl-2-aminohexane (20 g., b.p. 150-55°/10mm) by the Leuckart procedure³.

TABLE I

Ultraviolet spectra of 1,1'-methylene (or alkylmethylene)-bis-3-alkyl (or alkaryl)-3,4-dihydroisoquinolines (structural form II or III) and of the dehydrogenated products (structure IV).

Structural form.	R ₁ .	R ₂ .	$\lambda_{\max}$ (m μ) in	
			EtOH.	EtOH/HCl (0.04N).
II	Me	H	251(5.07)*	
"	Me	Me	320(4.39)	
"	Me	Et	329(4.30)	
"	Me	Pr	252(5.07)	
			346(4.51)	
"	Et	H	250(5.06)	
"	Et	Me	250(5.14)	
			330(4.69)	
"	H	PhCH ₂	252(4.76)	290(4.65)*
III	H	Me	260(5.20)	284(5.14)
			390(5.24)	408(5.26)
"	H	Et	260(5.20)	282(5.22)
			390(5.25)	412(5.29)
"	H	Pr	390(5.23)	280(5.13)
				412(5.28)
"	H	Pr ⁱ	392(5.24)	416(5.27)
"	H	Bu	256(5.00)	276(4.67)
			302(4.76)	416(4.71)
"	Me	H	..	276(5.19)
				440(5.17)
"	Me	Me	..	440(4.56)
"	Me	Et	..	436(4.42)
"	Me	Pr	..	280(5.05)
				450(4.50)
"	Et	H	..	278(4.91)
				440(4.77)
"	Et	Me	..	380(5.04)
				450(4.75)
IV	Me	H	280(4.85)	268(4.84)
			320(4.64)	330(4.89)
"	H	Et	268(4.78)	264(4.88)
			320(4.28)	338(4.51)
"	H	Pr	268(4.83)	272(4.94)
			318(4.05)	340(4.08)
"	Et	H	262(4.85)	268(4.89)
				332(4.34)

*Logs are in parentheses.

Malondi- α -methyl- β -phenethylamide (I: $R_1=H$, $R_2=Me$).—A mixture of 1-phenyl-2-aminopropane (13.5 g.) and ethyl malonate (8 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 180° for 4 hours. The resulting solid was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless plates (12.6 g.), m.p. 84-85°. (Found: N, 7.95. $C_{21}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.28%.)

The other amides have been similarly prepared and are described in Table II.

TABLE II
Malondiamides(I).

R_1 .	R_2 .	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
H	Et	105-106°	78%	$C_{23}H_{30}O_2N_2$	7.40	7.64
H	Pr	118-119°	83	$C_{25}H_{34}O_2N_2$	7.14	7.10
H	Pr ⁱ	108-109°	65	$C_{25}H_{34}O_2N_2$	7.18	7.10
H	Bu	101-102°	65	$C_{27}H_{38}O_2N_2$	6.26	6.83
H	Ph	184-85°	58	$C_{31}H_{30}O_2N_2$	5.94	6.06
H	PhCH ₂	140-41°	61	$C_{33}H_{34}O_2N_2$	5.72	5.71
Me	H	180-81°	82	$C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2$	8.75	8.64
Et	H	112-13°	74	$C_{21}H_{26}O_2N_2$	8.28	8.28
Ph	H	106-107°	72	$C_{25}H_{26}O_2N_2$	7.50	7.25
Me	Me	156-57°	65	$C_{22}H_{26}O_2N_2$	7.66	7.95
Me	Et	125-20°	58	$C_{24}H_{32}O_2N_2$	7.24	7.37
Me	Pr	104-105°	66	$C_{26}H_{36}O_2N_2$	6.84	6.86
Et	Me	182-83°	71	$C_{23}H_{30}O_2N_2$	7.88	7.65

1,1'-*Methylmethylene-bis-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline* (II: $R_1=Me$, $R_2=H$).—A mixture of (I: $R_1=Me$, $R_2=H$; 11 g.) and P_2O_5 (44 g.) in toluene (220 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath for 4 hours. The mixture was cooled in ice and treated with ice-water. The aqueous layer was separated, washed with ether, and filtered. The filtrate, on basification with NaOH, furnished a solid which crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. 103-104°. (Found: C, 83.02; H, 6.72; N, 9.48. $C_{20}H_{20}N_2$ requires C, 83.33; H, 6.94; N, 9.72%). The *dipicrate* crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 180-81°. (Found: C, 51.80; H, 3.31; N, 14.86. $C_{20}H_{20}N_2 \cdot 2C_5H_3O_7N_3$ requires C, 51.47; H, 3.49; N, 15.01%).

The other compounds of this series have been similarly prepared and are described in Table III.

TABLE III

1,1'-*Alkylmethylene-bis-3-alkyl(or alkaryl)-3,4-dihydroisoquinolines* (II).

R_1 .	R_2 .	B.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	Dipicrate.		
						M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
Me	Me	160-61°/1mm	$C_{22}H_{24}N_2$	N: 8.58%	8.88%	188-89°	N: 14.42%	14.47%
Me	Et	175-89°/10	$C_{24}H_{28}N_2$	N: 8.38	8.14	180-61°	N: 14.24	13.96
Me	Pr	180-85°/8-10	$C_{26}H_{32}N_2$	N: 7.38	7.53			
				C: 83.82	83.44			
Et	H	210-15°/13-14	$C_{21}H_{22}N_2$	H: 7.32	7.28			
				N: 8.89	9.27	167-68°	N: 14.32	14.74
Et	Me	197-95°/7-8	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2$	N: 8.12	8.84	164-65°	N: 14.02	14.22
							C: 58.72	59.31
H	PhCH ₂	160-65°/4-6	$C_{33}H_{30}N_2$	N: 5.81	6.17	151-52°	H: 4.02	3.95
							N: 12.24	12.28

The isoquinoline derivatives, which are found to exist in the form (III), have also been similarly prepared by following the method as in the case of (II: $R_1=Me$, $R_2=H$) and are described in Table IV. The characteristic feature of these compounds is their fine yellow colour.

TABLE IV
[3-Alkyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline-(1)]-[3'-alkyl-3',4'-dihydroisquinoline-(1')]-
methine-cyanines(III).

R_1 .	R_2 .	M.P./B.P.	Formula.	Found.		Reqd.		Monoplicate.		
				C:82.93%	H: 7.43	N: 9.10	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.	
H	Me	103-104°	$C_{21}H_{22}N_2$	83.44%	7.28	174-75°	C: 61.32%	61.01	H: 4.47	4.71
H	Et	69-70°	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2$	8.41	8.48	148-49°	N:12.88	13.18	N:12.53	12.52
H	Pr	75-70°	$C_{25}H_{30}N_2$	7.93	7.82					
H	Pr ⁱ	82-83°	$C_{25}H_{30}N_2$	7.80	7.82					
H	Bu	215-220°/10mm	$C_{27}H_{34}N_2$	83.71	8.81					
				8.89	8.81					
				7.32	7.25					
Ph	H	..	$C_{25}H_{22}N_2$	..	..	151-2°	C: 61.41	61.25	H: 4.23	4.32
							N:11.95	12.09		

1,1'-Methylmethylene-bis-isoquinoline (IV: $R_1=Me$, $R_2=H$).—A mixture of (II: $R_1=Me$, $R_2=H$; 4 g.), Pd-C(10%, 1g.) and tetralin (24 ml) was heated at 240° for 5 hours in an atmosphere of CO_2 . The mixture was filtered and washed with ether. From the filtrate the base was isolated by extraction with HCl(dil.) and basification with alkali. In order to ensure complete dehydrogenation, the above treatment with Pd-C was repeated 2-3 times till the m.p. of the dipicrate remained constant. The base distilled at 151-53°/9 mm. (Found: C, 84.92; H, 5.44; N, 9.95. $C_{20}H_{16}N_2$ requires C, 84.51; H, 5.03; N, 9.86%). The dipicrate was obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 215-16°. (Found: C, 51.93; H, 2.72; N, 14.98. $C_{20}H_{16}N_2 \cdot 2 C_6H_5O_2N_3$ requires C, 51.75; H, 2.96; N, 15.09%).

The other compounds of this series, which have been similarly prepared from the isoquinolines existing either in the form (II) or (III), are described in Table V.

TABLE V
1,1'-Alkyl (or aryl)-methylene-bis-3-alkylisoquinolines (IV).

R_1 .	R_2 .	B.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		Dipicrate		
				Found.	Reqd.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
H	Me	..	$C_{21}H_{18}N_2$	..	..	196-97°	N:15.12%	14.81%
H	Et	120°/6mm	$C_{23}H_{22}N_2$	8.36	8.58	161-62°	N:14.01	14.29
H	Pr	131-32°/4	$C_{25}H_{26}N_2$	7.67	7.91	145-46°	N:13.30	13.79
Et	H	112-15°/6-8	$C_{21}H_{16}N_2$	9.12	9.39	185-86°	N:14.63	14.81
Ph	H	..	$C_{25}H_{16}N_2$	..	..	171-72°	C:55.34	55.22
							H: 2.83	2.98
							N:13.61	13.93

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